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MS14 Nanomaterials FAIRification demonstration

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1. Introduction

Guidelines on how to exploit cloud solutions including the use of containerisation as a means to enhance sustainability, interoperability and re-usability of nanoinformatics models were developed in the WorldFAIR WP04 - Nanomaterials case study and presented in [Deliverable Report D4.2 - FAIRification of nanoinformatics tools and models recommendations](#)¹. In this milestone report (MS14), we provide a worked example of how containerisation and deployment to cloud platforms are achieved in practice for nanoinformatics models.

Sustainability of the nanoinformatics models and their accompanying microservices (software) is ensured by packaging them into [Docker containers](#)², including all system dependencies, such as other software or tools needed to run the microservice, and to link it to other services (in this case, models) that communicate with each other over a network. Development of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) provides additional flexibility for data transfer. An example of this is the use of input data to run the models and output data submitted to an underpinning database or as input to the next model in an integrated modelling workflow such as that developed in the Horizon 2020 [NanoSolveIT](#)³ project, where an Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA) was developed that integrated three computational approaches to generate data relevant to human health risk assessment (Tsiros et al., 2022). The three models integrated into the NanoSolveIT IATA were a multi-box aerosol model for prediction of indoor air concentrations of nanomaterials, a lung exposure model to determine the lung burden of nanomaterials following acute exposures and a physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model to determine the biodistribution of the nanomaterials to other organs over longer timescales following inhalation (Tsiros et al., 2022).

For the purpose of workflow demonstration, we have selected a stand-alone model for prediction of the interactions between nanomaterials using the Hamaker constant (Zhadanov, 2019), which is presented briefly in section 1.1 below, and is then used to demonstrate the containerisation and cloud deployment processes. This model for prediction of Hamaker constants is the basis of much of the computational effort to predict nanomaterials interactions with proteins, to form a biomolecule corona, which then determines how the nanomaterial interacts with cellular receptors and is internalised by cells (Power et al., 2019).

1.1. The NanoSolveIT Hamaker Constant prediction service

The van der Waals (vdW) interaction between nanomaterials (especially metal nanomaterials), may be appreciable, and may result in nanomaterial aggregation (Zhadanov, 2019). In the presence of biofluids, nanomaterials become rapidly surrounded by a protein corona (an adsorbed layer of biomolecules) that changes the vdW and hydration interaction of the nanomaterials, and thus their degree of agglomeration or stability in dispersion.

¹ [10.5281/zenodo.10629630](https://zenodo.org/record/10629630)

² <https://hub.docker.com/>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814572>

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Figure 1: Illustration of the NanoSolveIT tool for Hamaker constant calculation as it appears for the case study of ethanol nanoparticles in water. **Top:** A spherical Nanoparticle of phase 1 (grey colour) and a spherical Nanoparticle of phase 2 (dark blue colour) surrounded by a dispersion medium of phase 3 (wheat colour). Phase 1 consists of atoms illustrated with black and red colour spheres, Phase 2 consists of atoms illustrated with yellow, bright blue, and red colour spheres while Phase 3 consists of atoms illustrated with green, red, and brown colour spheres. **Middle:** Input area of the Hammaker tool. Background grey, blue and wheat colours correspond to the phases 1, 2 and 3 of the nanomaterials used in the calculation, respectively. **Bottom:** Illustration of where the results - Hamaker constants representing with symbol A and units 10^{-20}J appear once the model is run.

To calculate the vdW interaction, one needs the Hamaker constants (Hamaker, 1937), which characterise the interaction of two materials of interest and a medium between them. As a rule, accurate determination of these constants is difficult. On the length scale of interest, the Hamaker constants depend weakly on the nanomaterial size. Hamaker constants for nanomaterials with an acquired protein corona are not generally available in the literature (Zhadanov, 2019), and thus there is a need for models to predict Hamaker constants, as a basis for predicting nanomaterials coronas and cellular interactions.

The Hamaker constant can be used as a descriptor of the effect of the dispersion medium on the attraction of two nanomaterials, and its rapid calculation can be achieved using atomistic Force-Fields available in literature (e.g., UFF⁴, DREIDING⁵, CHARMM⁶, OPLS⁷). In order to run the model, the user selects the nanomaterials compositions, and phases (1, 2, 3) as shown schematically in Figure 1. Phase 1 can be selected from a list of nanomaterials/phases such as Ag, Al, Au, Cu, Fe, Pb, Pd, Pt, TiO₂ (anatase, rutile), SiO₂(amorphous, quartz), ZnS (sphalerite), Fe₂O₃ (hematite), Fe₃O₄ (magnetite), ZnO (wurtzite), PTMO (polytetramethylene oxide), Chitosan, PLGA (poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid), PEG (polyethylene glycol) and cholesterol. If the material of interest to the user is not in the list, the user can manually insert its properties (i.e., density, chemical elements, stoichiometry). Because Force-Fields often have more than one atom type for a specific chemical element (i.e., according to its chemical environment), a special treatment (using the most generic atom type of the Force-Field) has been applied to make this tool as generic as possible. The same process is used for phase 2, whereby the user can insert another material.

To facilitate the calculation of Hamaker constants for use in predictive modelling of nanomaterials safety and for generation of protein corona data, within the NanoSolveIT project, an Application Programming Interface (API) was implemented for the Hamaker model, as per the recommendation in [WorldFAIR Deliverable D4.2](#)⁸ on FAIRification of nanoinformatics models and software (see section 3.6.2 of D4.2 for details). The APIs provides programmable access to the model, meaning that users and developers can streamlining processes such as data ingestion, model execution, and result analysis, and integrate this model with other models into automated nanoinformatics workflows.

⁴ Rappe, A.K., C. J. Casewit, C.J., K. S. Colwell, K.S., Goddard III, W. A., Skiff, W.M. UFF, a full periodic table force field for molecular mechanics and molecular dynamics simulations. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1992, 114, 25, 10024–10035. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00051a040>

⁵ Mayo, S.L., Olafson, B.D., Goddard III, W.A. DREIDING: A Generic Force Field for Molecular Simulations. *Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 1990, 94 (26): 8897–8909. <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100389a010>.

⁶ <https://www.charmm.org/>

⁷ Lu, C., Wu, C., Ghoreishi, D., Chen, W., Wang, L., Damm, W., Ross, G.A., Dahlgren, M.K., Russell, E., Von Bargen, C.D., Abel, R., Friesner, R.A., Harder, E.D. OPLS4: Improving Force Field Accuracy on Challenging Regimes of Chemical Space *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* 2021 17 (7), 4291-4300. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00302

⁸ Lynch, I., & Afantitis, A. (2024). WorldFAIR (D4.2) FAIRification of nanoinformatics tools and models recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10629631>

Each NanoSolveIT model has a unique Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) and identifier (ID), which ensures that every model can be distinctly referenced and accessed. This unique identification is crucial for managing and interacting with the models programmatically via RESTful APIs, following the principles of OpenAPI specification. The OpenAPI standard facilitates the creation, documentation, and consumption of APIs, enhancing the accessibility and interoperability of the models.

1.2. API actions for NanoSolveIT models

The API for interacting with NanoSolveIT models supports the following HTTP actions, each serving a specific purpose in managing the lifecycle and usage of the models:

1. GET: This action retrieves information about a specific model using its unique ID. It can be used to obtain details such as model metadata, description, parameters, and current status. This is essential for users to understand the capabilities and requirements of the model before execution.
2. PUT: This action updates the information of an existing model. It can be used to modify the model's parameters, update its metadata, or change its configuration. This ensures that the model can evolve over time and adapt to new requirements or improvements.

NanoSolveIT REST APIs

POST /restapi Returns a sequence of images per input image and results

Returns param

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
body	Example Value Model
object (body)	<pre>{ "inputImage": { "imageInBase64": "string", "imageFormat": "string" }, "nmType": "string", "compBranch": "string", "pxIsPerNRatio": 0, "thresholdingMethod": "string", "thresholdValue": 0, "distanceMergeThreshold": 0, "gaussSize": 0, "sizeMergeThreshold": 0, "minimumSegmentArea": 0, "maximumSegmentArea": 0, "removeOutliers": true, "xdsigmaS": 0, "ydsigmaS": 0 }</pre>

Parameter content type: application/json

Figure 2: Example of POST API for the NanoXtarct model.

3. **POST:** This action creates predictions using the model. It involves submitting the necessary input parameters to the model, which then processes these inputs and generates the desired outputs. The POST action can also store the results of the model run, making it available for future reference or further analysis, as shown in Figure 2.
4. **DELETE:** This action removes a model from the system. It is useful for managing the lifecycle of models, especially for deprecated or obsolete models that are no longer needed. This action ensures that the model repository remains clean and up-to-date.

The implementation of these API actions using the OpenAPI specification offers several benefits, which include:

- **Standardisation:** OpenAPI provides a standardised way to define and document APIs, making it easier for developers and users to understand and interact with the models.
- **Interoperability:** By adhering to OpenAPI standards, the NanoSolveIT models can seamlessly integrate with other systems and tools, promoting data and model interoperability.
- **Automation:** The use of APIs allows for the automation of model interactions, enabling streamlined workflows and integration into larger computational pipelines.
- **Documentation:** OpenAPI comes with built-in support for generating interactive documentation, allowing users to explore and test the APIs directly from a web interface.
- **Flexibility:** The range of HTTP actions (GET, PUT, POST, DELETE) provides comprehensive control over the models, from retrieval and updates to execution and deletion.

Incorporating the OpenAPI standard aligns with the FAIR principles of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. By providing clear, standardised documentation and automated interaction capabilities, OpenAPI enhances the findability and accessibility of the models. The standardised API interactions promote interoperability with other tools and systems, facilitating seamless integration into broader workflows. Finally, the ability to easily retrieve, update, execute, and delete models ensures that they remain reusable across different applications and use cases. This adherence to FAIR principles not only improves the usability of the NanoSolveIT models but also ensures their broad utility and sustainability within the scientific community.

As also noted in WorldFAIR D4.2, the model can be further FAIRified by making it available (and sustainable) by containerisation. The result of this milestone focuses on the process of containerisation to guide the community through the process. We note that there are many tutorials on containerisation⁹, and don't intend to replicate those here, but rather we provide a worked example for the Hammaker model described above, to make the workflow more concrete.

For the sake of completeness, and to map to the various approaches to FAIRify models and their software described in WorldFAIR D4.2, we note also that we have provided a Graphical user interface (GUI) for the Hamaker model, which is also accessible to users who lack the coding skills to make use of the API, and is available via the NanoSolveIT Cloud at <https://hamaker.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>. The selection of the nanoparticles and dispersion medium

⁹ <https://www.bmc.com/blogs/what-is-a-container-containerization-explained/>

materials (i.e., their density in g/cm^3 and stoichiometry) as well as the Force-Fields describing their interactions are selected through the GUI.

2. Step-by-step workflow for containerisation and deployment of nanoinformatics models

In the sections below, we describe the workflow for containerisation of an individual model as a Docker image, using the Hamaker model described above for illustration, and its deployment on a single computer. As a further step to increase the accessibility of the model, we then present the process for its integration into a modelling workflow, also called orchestration, whereby the output of the Hamaker model is used as input for other models, such as prediction of a nanomaterial's protein corona.

The orchestration process utilises Kubernetes, which enables the Hamaker model (and other models that it is planned to interact with) to be presented as a “pod” (the smallest deployable units of computing that can be created and managed in Kubernetes, whereby a pod represents a single instance of a running application in the cluster - see optional step 3B below and further technical details in Section 3.1 below). The steps in the model containerisation workflow are shown schematically and summarised in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Step by step procedure for containerisation of a model to increase its Accessibility and ensure its long(er) term sustainability.

2.1. Step 1: Preparing the Model

The first step involves preparing the model code: ensuring it is clean, well-documented, and that all dependencies are clearly specified, particularly those related to data input required to run the

model and data output from the model to ensure that the data is suitable as input for the next model in the specific workflow. To facilitate this step, it is essential to create a requirements file listing all dependencies needed for the model. Testing the model locally is crucial to verify that it runs correctly. This includes writing and running unit tests and integration tests to ensure the main functionalities of the model are covered and function as expected. A major driver for containerisation is the ability to integrate the model with other related models, and thus it is important to test the interplay of the specific service with other services, which provide the input or use the output and that this should then be modelled in the APIs. While this Milestone report only describes the APIs and deployment, we note that there are many other ‘FAIR for nanoinformatics’ guidelines, with more information available from [WorldFAIR Deliverable D4.2](#)¹⁰.

To ensure the software adheres to FAIR principles, it must comply with specific guidelines. Firstly, the software must be retrievable by its identifier using a standardised communications protocol. This protocol should be open, free, and universally implementable, and should accommodate authentication and authorisation procedures when necessary. Additionally, the software must be capable of reading, writing, and exchanging data in a manner that aligns with domain-relevant community standards, ensuring appropriate interaction with data as per the standards and practices of the relevant domain. Moreover, the software must be documented with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. It should possess a clear and accessible licence and be associated with detailed provenance, documenting its history and origin. The software must also comply with domain-relevant community standards, ensuring its suitability and effectiveness for its intended application. Adhering to these guidelines allows the software to be listed in a registry, thereby enhancing its discoverability and usability within the community. This workflow underscores the significance of standardised protocols, comprehensive documentation, and adherence to community standards in the development and deployment of software models, ensuring they are accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

2.2. Step 2: ‘Dockerizing’ the Model

Containerisation (Cito, 2016) is a core technology that produces standard units of software, to package up code and all its dependencies, and ensure that the microservices run quickly and reliably from one computing environment to another. The freely available Docker containerisation tool was adopted in NanoSolveIT. This technology enabled the development of various container Docker images, which are lightweight, standalone, executable packages and include everything needed to run the microservices: code, runtime, system tools, system libraries and settings.

The software required to run docker, [docker Desktop](#)¹¹, is freely available and the docker Engine (<https://docs.docker.com/engine/>) can be installed on infrastructures ranging from Virtual Machines (VMs) on servers to personal computers, and can run on most operating systems. On Windows, docker can be installed and run on virtual machines (VMs) and a Windows installer installs all the

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10629631>

¹¹ <https://www.docker.com/products/docker-desktop>

requirements. Docker also runs on almost any Linux distribution (Ubuntu, Debian etc.) and on Apple computers. In this way, model and software developers can ensure that their models and software will run on any infrastructure and personal computer thus ensuring maximum utility to stakeholders across industry and regulatory authorities.

The NanoSolveIT docker hub is accessible at <https://hub.docker.com/u/nanosolveit>, and hosts the docker images (Figure 4) of the microservices developed to date.

Repository Name	Security	Stars	Downloads	Visibility
novamechanics / lungexposure	Security unknown	0	197	Public
novamechanics / sb4n	Security unknown	0	5	Public
novamechanics / nanoxtract	Security unknown	0	372	Public
novamechanics / exposurepbpk	Security unknown	0	36	Public
novamechanics / mszeta	Security unknown	0	3	Public
novamechanics / cellviability	Security unknown	0	5	Public
novamechanics / ecotox	Security unknown	0	44	Public
novamechanics / dermal	Security unknown	0	52	Public
novamechanics / zetapotential	Security unknown	0	33	Public

Figure 4: A screenshot of some of the NanoSolveIT docker hub (models and tools developed by NovaMechanics).

There are many different aspects to be considered when preparing for ‘dockerization’, but here we note the need for a complete understanding of the requirements a service has and what components would be needed. For example, is persistent storage something the service needs to provide or can it just be restarted from scratch without the need to recover its history? As the service needs to expose its API or GUI, this might require careful thinking about authentication and authorisation.

Next, Docker needs to be installed on the user’s system. Docker Desktop can be downloaded and installed from Docker’s official website. Once Docker is set up, a Dockerfile is created in the root directory of the user’s project. This file defines the environment and instructions for building the Docker image. The Dockerfile specifies the base image, sets the working directory, copies the project files into the container, installs the dependencies, exposes necessary ports, and defines the command to run the model. After creating the Dockerfile, the Docker image is built using the Docker build command. This process packages the model and its dependencies into a portable image. It is then important to test the Docker image locally by running it and ensuring the application functions correctly when accessed.

2.3. Step 3: Pushing Docker image to Docker Hub

To make the Docker image available for deployment, it must be pushed to Docker Hub. Docker Hub is a cloud-based registry service that allows the storage, management, and distribution of Docker container images. This process involves creating an account on Docker Hub, tagging the Docker image, and then pushing the tagged image to the repository.

First, an account on Docker Hub must be created by visiting the Docker Hub website and signing up if necessary. Then the user must verify their email address and complete the account setup process. Next, the user should open their terminal or command prompt and log in to their Docker Hub account using the command `docker login`. They will be prompted to enter their Docker Hub username and password. Successful login will be confirmed.

Before pushing the image to Docker Hub, it needs to be tagged with the Docker Hub username and repository name. Tagging helps in uniquely identifying the image. To tag the Docker image, the command `docker tag <local-image-name> <dockerhub-username>/<repository-name>:<tag>` is used. For example, if the local image is named "mymodel-image", the Docker Hub username is "johnsmith", and the repository name is "mymodel-repo" with the tag "latest", the command would be `docker tag mymodel-image johnsmith/mymodel-repo:latest`. In this command, `<local-image-name>` is the name of the local Docker image, `<dockerhub-username>` is the Docker Hub username, `<repository-name>` is the desired name of the repository on Docker Hub, and `<tag>` is typically set to "latest" but can be any identifier chosen by the user.

After tagging the Docker image, it can be pushed to Docker Hub using the command `docker push <dockerhub-username>/<repository-name>:<tag>`. Continuing with the previous example, the command would be `docker push johnsmith/mymodel-repo:latest`. The terminal will display the progress of the push operation, showing the layers of the Docker image being uploaded to the remote repository. Once the push operation is complete, the image will be available in the Docker Hub repository. To verify the image on Docker Hub, the user should log in to their Docker Hub account through the web interface and navigate to the 'Repositories' section from the Docker Hub dashboard. The newly pushed image should be listed under the specified repository name. By clicking on the repository name, the user can view the details of the image. The repository page provides information such as the available tags, the size of the image, and the Dockerfile used to create the image. The user can also manage the repository settings, add collaborators, and control the visibility (public or private) of the repository. Using Docker Hub offers several benefits. By pushing the Docker image to Docker Hub, it becomes accessible from anywhere, facilitating easy deployment across different environments and infrastructures. Docker Hub allows the maintenance of multiple versions of images using tags, enabling rollbacks to previous versions if needed. Repositories on Docker Hub can be shared with team members, enabling collaborative development and deployment of containerized applications. Docker Hub also integrates seamlessly with other tools and services, including Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines, which automate the process of building, testing, and deploying Docker images.

Figure 5. Hamaker application available at Docker Hub, providing stable and long-term access to the model, thus addressing the Accessibility principle of FAIR, as well as facilitating its Findability and Re-Usability for inclusion in other modelling workflows.

2.4. Optional Step 3b: Deploying with Kubernetes

Kubernetes is a useful approach for models that are high-performance and have high user-traffic. [Kubernetes](https://kubernetes.io/)¹² was noted in WorldFAIR D4.2 as one solution for container orchestration (linking of models in specific sequences or workflows). With the Docker image available on Docker Hub, the next step is deploying it using Kubernetes.

Kubernetes and kubectl, the command-line tool for Kubernetes, need to be installed by following instructions on Kubernetes' official website. Kubernetes configuration files are then created to define the Deployment and Service for the model. The Deployment configuration specifies how many replicas of the pod (the smallest deployable unit in Kubernetes) should run, and details about the container image and ports. The Service configuration defines how to access the pods and exposes them via a load balancer. These configuration files are applied to the Kubernetes cluster using kubectl commands. This process deploys the pods and services as defined in the configuration files. It is important to verify the deployment by checking the status of the pods and ensuring they are running correctly. The external IP address of the service is then retrieved to access the deployed application.

2.5. Step 4: Running Docker on a single computer

Docker can be efficiently utilised on a single computer to run containerised applications, including nanoinformatics models. This section outlines the steps required to set up Docker on a personal computer and run Docker containers, ensuring the model can be executed locally with all necessary dependencies.

To begin, users need to download Docker Desktop from the official Docker website. The appropriate installer should be selected based on the operating system in use, whether it be Windows, macOS, or Linux. Once downloaded, the installation process is straightforward. On Windows, the installer will prompt the user to allow changes to the system and will install all required components, including the Docker Engine. On macOS, the installation involves opening the downloaded file and dragging the Docker icon to the Applications folder, from where Docker Desktop can be started. For Linux users, the installation process may vary slightly depending on the distribution, typically involving the use of package managers like **apt** for Ubuntu or **yum** for CentOS. Detailed instructions for Linux installations are available on the Docker documentation site.

After installation, the first run may require system permissions and a system restart. To verify that Docker has been installed correctly, users can open a terminal or command prompt and run the command to check Docker's version. Additionally, running a test image, such as "hello-world," will confirm that Docker can pull and run containers, displaying a success message. With Docker installed, the next step is to build and run a Docker image. This process begins with creating a Dockerfile in the root directory of the project. The Dockerfile defines the environment and

¹² <https://kubernetes.io/>

instructions for building the Docker image, specifying the base image, setting the working directory, copying project files into the container, installing dependencies, exposing necessary ports, and defining the command to run the model. Once the Dockerfile is created, the Docker image can be built by navigating to the directory containing the Dockerfile and running the appropriate build command in the terminal. Docker will process the Dockerfile, installing dependencies and preparing the environment. After building the image, the container can be run by executing the run command in the terminal, which will start the container and map the container's ports to the local machine. The model should now be running in a Docker container and can be accessed through a web browser or any tool capable of making HTTP requests. Managing Docker containers involves listing running containers, stopping them, and removing stopped containers as needed. These tasks are performed using Docker commands in the terminal, allowing users to control the lifecycle of their containers efficiently.

Running Docker on a single computer offers several advantages. The Docker container ensures that the model runs in the same environment every time, eliminating inconsistencies and the common "works on my machine" issues. Docker containers run in isolated environments, preventing conflicts with other software on the system. Docker simplifies the process of setting up and running applications, as all dependencies are packaged within the container, providing ease of use. Additionally, Docker images are portable and can be transferred between different machines, ensuring the model can run anywhere Docker is supported.

2.6. Step 5: Automating the workflow

To streamline and automate the containerisation and deployment process, a Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline can be set up. Tools like Jenkins, GitHub Actions, or GitLab CI can automate the build, test, and deployment processes. Integrating Docker and Kubernetes commands into the CI/CD pipeline configuration ensures that the workflow is automated and efficient. Finally, implementing monitoring and logging is essential for maintaining the performance and health of the deployed model. By following these steps, the nanoinformatics models are effectively containerised and deployed, ensuring they are scalable, interoperable, and reusable across different environments and infrastructures.

This workflow, summarised in Figure 6 for deployment of models to the [Enolas Cloud Platform](https://www.enalcloud.com/)¹³ as an example of deployment, not only enhances the sustainability of the models but also ensures their broad utility and accessibility for stakeholders across various sectors.

¹³ <https://www.enalcloud.com/>

Figure 6: Workflow for Containerisation, Deployment, and FAIRification of Models on the [Enalos Cloud Platform](https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/)¹⁴.

3. Packaging nanoinformatics models and tools as microservices

3.1. NanoSolveIT Kubernetes services

In Kubernetes, a Service is an abstraction which defines a logical set of Pods and a policy by which to access them. Therefore, a service may expose one or more pods. A service enables a group of pods, which provide specific functions (web services, image processing, etc.) to be assigned a name and unique IP address (clusterIP). The set of Pods targeted by a Service is determined by a selector.

The NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster currently (May 2024) contains 50 services with a screenshot presenting 10 of these webservices shown in Figure 7. Figure 8 presents the YAML¹⁵ file declaring the Hamaker service in the NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster.

¹⁴ <https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/>

¹⁵ <https://yaml.org/>

nanopot	doxviability-app	ClusterIP	10.100.65.88	<none>	80/TCP	374d
nanopot	nanobio-service	ClusterIP	10.104.51.11	<none>	80/TCP	426d
nanopot	nanoinhale-service	ClusterIP	10.107.84.29	<none>	80/TCP	426d
nanopot	nanopot-app	ClusterIP	10.107.2.31	<none>	80/TCP	426d
nanopot	sbpot-service	ClusterIP	10.99.119.168	<none>	80/TCP	426d
nanopot	viablcels-service	ClusterIP	10.101.13.187	<none>	80/TCP	426d
nanopot	zetapot-app	ClusterIP	10.104.166.178	<none>	80/TCP	426d
novanano-apps	aerosol-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.103.135.97	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	bridgedb-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.103.213.71	<none>	80/TCP	437d
novanano-apps	cellviability-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.106.158.167	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	dermal-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.96.28.41	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	ecotox-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.104.170.117	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	exposureepbk-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.111.54.168	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	facetcytotoxicity-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.108.45.215	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	hamaker-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.101.247.44	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	lungexp-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.101.248.140	<none>	80/TCP	180d
novanano-apps	mszeta-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.101.208.120	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	nanoxtract-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.98.227.91	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.104.100.77	<none>	80/TCP	437d
novanano-apps	sb4n-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.100.12.189	<none>	80/TCP	321d
novanano-apps	zetapotential-novanano-service	ClusterIP	10.109.30.75	<none>	80/TCP	321d
oidc	keycloak	NodePort	10.102.247.244	<none>	8080:30100/TCP	437d
oidc	postgres-oidc	ClusterIP	10.98.248.200	<none>	5432/TCP	437d
qsarlab	qsar-service	NodePort	10.108.36.6	<none>	8050:32549/TCP	426d
shiny-apps	eutopia-service	NodePort	10.107.197.93	<none>	3838:32470/TCP	438d
shiny-apps	funmappone-service	NodePort	10.100.178.163	<none>	3838:30259/TCP	437d
shiny-apps	vythos-service	NodePort	10.103.237.116	<none>	3838:31765/TCP	443d
virtuoso	virtuoso-exposed	NodePort	10.111.101.213	<none>	8890:30144/TCP	426d

Figure 7: A screenshot presenting 10 (of the total of 50) services in the NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster.

```

kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: hamaker-novanano-service
  namespace: novanano-apps
spec:
  selector:
    app: hamaker-novanano-app
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      name: http
      port: 80
      targetPort: 8080

```

Figure 8: YAML file declaring the Hamaker service in the NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster.

3.2. Using Kubernetes for complex model integrations

3.2.1. Container orchestration through Kubernetes

For complex model integrations, the use of Kubernetes¹⁶ is highly recommended. Kubernetes facilitates the reuse of "pods," which are the smallest deployable units of computing that can be created and managed in Kubernetes. Pods essentially represent software services (models) provided in the form of Docker images. Each pod encapsulates one or more containers, storage resources, a

¹⁶ <https://kubernetes.io/>

unique network IP, and options that govern how the containers should run. The advantages of using Kubernetes for complex model integrations are significant. Kubernetes allows for the deployment of pods, which are modular units that can be reused across multiple services. This modularity and reusability make Kubernetes particularly useful for managing complex systems with numerous interconnected components. A single pod can represent an instance of a running application in the cluster, and multiple pods can be deployed to serve the same function, enhancing scalability and reliability. Kubernetes supports horizontal scaling, allowing users to easily scale applications up or down by adding or removing pod instances. This dynamic scaling is essential for applications that experience variable workloads, ensuring optimal resource utilisation and performance. Furthermore, Kubernetes ensures high availability of applications by automatically replacing or rescheduling failed or crashed pods. The system continuously monitors the health of pods and nodes, redistributing workloads as necessary to maintain service continuity. Kubernetes provides built-in load balancing and service discovery mechanisms. When multiple instances of a pod are running, Kubernetes can distribute traffic among them to ensure efficient utilisation of resources and consistent application performance.

Services in Kubernetes are defined as abstractions that provide a stable IP address and DNS name, enabling seamless communication between different parts of an application. Kubernetes also supports automated rollouts and rollbacks for application updates. Users can define deployment strategies to update applications without downtime, and in the event of a failure, Kubernetes can automatically roll back to a previous stable version, ensuring minimal disruption. In addition, Kubernetes provides sophisticated resource management capabilities, allowing users to define resource limits and requests for each pod. This ensures that applications have the necessary resources to run efficiently while preventing any single pod from monopolising the system's resources. Kubernetes has self-healing capabilities that automatically detect and replace failed containers. Pods that fail to pass health checks are terminated and replaced with new ones, maintaining the desired state of the application. Moreover, Kubernetes uses ConfigMaps¹⁷ and Secrets¹⁸ to manage application configurations and sensitive information, such as passwords and API keys. These configurations can be dynamically updated without requiring redeployment of the pods, enabling easier management of application settings.

A pod in Kubernetes is a logical unit that encapsulates one or more tightly coupled containers that share the same network namespace and storage resources. Each pod is assigned a unique IP address, which allows the containers within the pod to communicate with each other using localhost. Pods are ephemeral by nature, meaning they are designed to be created, destroyed, and replaced as needed. In a Kubernetes cluster, pods can be deployed and managed using controllers, such as Deployments, StatefulSets, and DaemonSets. These controllers define the desired state of the pods and ensure that the cluster maintains this state. For instance, a Deployment can specify that a certain number of pod replicas should be running at all times, and Kubernetes will

¹⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/configuration/configmap/>

¹⁸ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/configuration/secret/>

automatically create or terminate pods to match this specification. Pods can also be grouped and exposed as a single service, which provides a stable endpoint for accessing the application. This abstraction allows users to interact with the service without needing to manage the individual pods directly, simplifying the deployment and scaling processes. Consider a complex nanoinformatics model that involves multiple interconnected components, such as data ingestion, processing, analysis, and visualisation services. Each of these components can be encapsulated in a Docker image and deployed as a pod in a Kubernetes cluster.

By defining services for each component, Kubernetes can manage the communication between these services, ensuring seamless data flow and integration. As the workload increases, Kubernetes can scale the number of pod instances for the data processing service to handle the additional load. If any pod fails, Kubernetes will automatically replace it, maintaining the overall health and availability of the application. Configuration changes, such as updating the parameters for data analysis, can be managed through ConfigMaps, allowing for dynamic updates without redeploying the pods.

3.2.2. NanoSolveIT Kubernetes pods

Pods are the smallest deployable units of computing that can be created and managed in Kubernetes (docker images). A Pod represents a single instance of a running application in the cluster. Note that one service can be composed out of multiple docker images and that defining this specific architecture, which keeps it simple but at the same time offers all required elements, is one of the most complicated tasks in containerisation. The pod then represents the implementation of this architecture choice and is only operable if all the elements are available (co-created and co-scheduled). A Pod's contents are always co-located and co-scheduled, and run in a shared context.

The NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster currently contains 55 pods (a screenshot presenting 10 of the NanoSolveIT pods deployed is shown in Figure 9).

nanopot	cytotox-app-6b678c4456-b6p6g	1/1	Running	1	426d
nanopot	doxrelease-app-546d78dfbd-c225f	1/1	Running	1	374d
nanopot	doxviability-app-59f7d66948-v6pmp	1/1	Running	1	374d
nanopot	nanobio-app-999d8487b-zbck7	1/1	Running	1	426d
nanopot	nanoinhale-app-6fd84b5f88-qrlj4	1/1	Running	1	426d
nanopot	nanopot-app-7fbdc67444-svnh5	1/1	Running	1	426d
nanopot	sbpot-app-5b66f87b8-xjdr5	1/1	Running	1	426d
nanopot	viabilecells-app-775598b476-hmmjr	1/1	Running	1	426d
nanopot	zetapot-app-754496c788-ktb6r	1/1	Running	1	426d
novanano-apps	aerosol-novanano-app-8c56f7c4d-ljbns	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	bridgedb-novanano-app-67ff688d9-vctqq	0/1	ImagePullBackOff	0	437d
novanano-apps	cellviability-novanano-app-5587986c5b-r2ngg	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	dermal-novanano-app-66c9ddfd6-zn2vl	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	ecotox-novanano-app-768d9f67f8-l7542	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	exposurepbpk-novanano-app-565d7d75c4-grpgp	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	facetcytotoxicity-novanano-app-5dd45747c6-8ccl9	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	hamaker-novanano-app-575b48b98f-8hdfh	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	lungexp-novanano-app-78b865ff88-hsv9w	1/1	Running	1	180d
novanano-apps	mszeta-novanano-app-5c474b4c86-cpbdq	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	nanoxtract-novanano-app-578c8bb46b-6bsfb	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	novanano-app-6bc99955b8-svbqp	1/1	Running	1	437d
novanano-apps	sb4n-novanano-app-6b5ff78bf8-bzgv9	1/1	Running	1	321d
novanano-apps	zetapotential-novanano-app-5bb694f68d-bngb5	1/1	Running	1	321d
oidc	keycloak-56f698fb6c-9xqx8	0/1	ErrImagePull	0	437d
oidc	postgres-oidc-647b96f946-wslh7	1/1	Running	1	437d
qsarlab	qsar-app-7fb95fd9cb-fvm6h	1/1	Running	1	426d
shiny-apps	eutopia-app-6cffd77f84-7ffzk	1/1	Running	1	438d
shiny-apps	funmappone-app-5565c5948f-gl5fr	1/1	Running	1	437d
shiny-apps	vythos-app-57448c67b4-62j7z	1/1	Running	1	443d
virtuoso	virtuoso-deployment-6b947944b5-zmmmc	1/1	Running	1	426d

Figure 9: A screenshot presenting 10 of the pods in the NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster.

3.2.3. NanoSolveIT Kubernetes deployments

Deployments are used to instruct Kubernetes on how to create or modify instances of the pods that hold a containerized application. Deployments can scale the number of replica pods to meet the computational requirements (for example multiple users might use replica pods), enable rollout of updated code in a controlled manner, or roll back to an earlier deployment version if necessary. Figure 9 presents the YAML file declaring the Hamaker deployment in the NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster.

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: hamaker-novanano-app
  namespace: novanano-apps
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: hamaker-novanano-app
  replicas: 1
  template:
    metadata:
      name: hamaker-novanano-app
    labels:
      app: hamaker-novanano-app
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: hamaker-novanano-app
          image: novamechanics/hamaker
          imagePullPolicy: Always
      ports:
        - containerPort: 8080
          name: http
```

Figure 9: YAML file declaring the Hamaker deployment in the NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster.

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